

PASC24 paper artifacts

The following is a description of artifacts necessary to reproduce the paper “A portable and efficient Lagrangian particle capability for idealized atmospheric phenomena”

The directory structure is as follows:

BASE/src

Contains all the source code necessary to build the BASE (pre-optimized) version of CM1 on either CPU or GPU

BASE/run

The run directory in which the BASE version of CM1 is built and executed

OPT/src

Contains all the source code necessary to build the OPT (optimized) version of CM1 on either CPU or GPU

OPT/run

The run directory in which the OPT version of CM1 is built and executed

data/	Output log files for a number of the plots included in the paper
plotting/	Plotting scripts to generate the plots included in the paper
scripts/	Several useful scripts used to either execute or process data from the log files

We next describe the contents of each of the main subdirectories:

{BASE,OPT}/src/

The ‘src’ directory contains the source code for CM1 and is the directory in which the make command is executed. The building of CM1 is controlled by a Makefile with options. Several example build commands for common targets are as follows:

Intel compiler, CPU

```
make -j 24 FC=ifort USE_MPI=true
```

NVHPC compiler, CPU

```
make -j 24 FC=nvfortran USE_MPI=true
```

NVHPC compiler, GPU using OpenACC

```
make -j 24 FC=nvfortran USE_MPI=true USE_OPENACC=true  
GPU_TYPE=a100
```

Note several additional target build options are also available in the Makefile

{BASE,OPT}/run/

The 'run' directory is the location where the CM1 executable is built. It is also the location of the batch scripts and necessary input files. Configuration of CM1 is controlled through the use of a namelist file. The following runscripts can be used to reproduce the various plots:

Figure-9,10:

```
BASE/run/derecho.figure9-10.ngpu8.sh  
OPT/run/derecho.ngpu8.sh
```

Figure-11:

```
OPT/run/derecho.ngpu{4,16,36,64,100,144,256,324}.sh
```

Table-1,2:

```
OPT/run/derecho.ncpu32k_power.sh  
OPT/run/derecho.ngpu256_power.sh
```

data/Figure-8/
data/Figure-9,10/
data/Figure-11/
data/Table-1/CPU
data/Table-1/GPU
data/Table-2/CPU
data/Table-2/GPU

The data subdirectory contains the log files used to generate plots and data in two tables presented in the paper. Unfortunately, the naming convention used for the log files is not consistent but contains sufficient information to determine the corresponding data point in the plots. For example, consider the file 'ngpu8.2m.opt-gpu.log'. This log file corresponds to the run on 8 GPUs, with 2 Million droplets using the OPT-GPU version of the code. Unfortunately, most of the timing information presented in the paper, including Figures 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and Table 1 is copied from the log files into either Python plotting routines or into the paper in the case of Table 1. in the plotting subdirectory manually. The

correspondence timer names and plotted values for Figures 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and Table 1 are described first. Afterward, the approach used for Table 2 will be described

plotting/Figure-8
plotting/Figure-9/
plotting/Figure-10/
plotting/Figure-11/

Python-based plotting scripts are provided in the plotting subdirectory. We indicate the translation between timing information in the log files that are used in each plotting file next.

Figure-8: The value for 'Total time' is used

Figure-9: The value for 'droplet' is used

Figure-10: The value for 'dropletA' is used.

Figure-11: The values from the log files and their corresponding values in the plot are:

'Total time' → Total
, 'sound' → Sound
, 'advect' → Advection
, 'turb' → Turbulence
'Write', → File IO
'Droplet+parcels' → Droplets
'Diag' → Diagnostics
'Other' → Other
'mp_total' → Bndry exchange
'dropComm' → DropletComm

Figure-12: The values from the log files and their corresponding values in the plot are:

'Total time' → Total
, 'sound' → Sound
, 'advect' → Advection
, 'turb' → Turbulence
'Write', → File IO
'Droplet+parcels' → Droplets
'Diag' → Diagnostics
'Other' → Other
'mp_total' → Bndry exchange
'dropComm' → DropletComm

Table-1: The values from the log files and their corresponding values in the Table are:

'Total time' → Total
'sound' → AcousticSolver
'Turb' → Turbulence
'Advect' → Advection
'Write' → File IO
'domndiag+stat' → Diagnostics
'load-imb' → Load-imbalance
'droplet+droplet!' → Microphysics
'dropC1+dropC2+dropC3+dropC4' → Comm
'statD' → Diagnostics (Lagrangian droplets)

Table-2:

Unlike the previously described Figures and Table 1, the values for Table 2 are calculated by running the 'energy.py' script found in the scripts directory.

An example invocation of the energy.py script which calculates the amount of energy used by the memory subsystem is as follows

```
./energy.py -f 'memory*.log.*'
```

Log files that record the energy used by the accelerators (accel*_energy.log.*), the CPU (cpu_energy.log.*), the memory subsystem (memory_energy.log.*), and the total energy consumed (energy.log.*) are found in the CPU and GPU subdirectories.

scripts/

The scripts directory contains several scripts that are useful for measuring the characteristics of the execution of the model.

logEnergy.sh:

This script is started before the actual application is executed and collects energy usage a periodic intervals. For an example of usage please see the file ????.

energy.py:

A Python script that totals up energy measurements from log files generated by the logEnergy.sh script.

nsys_wrap:

A wrapper script that is used to activate NVIDIA's Nsight Systems profiling

ncu_wrap:

A wrapper script that is used to activate NVIDIA's Nsight Compute profiling.

env.{cpu,gpu}

Module settings for both the CPU and GPU run.